
**Status of Workers in The Krishna Verla Magasvargiya Sahkari Soot Girni
Ltd (Palus) Dist. Sangli**

Dr. Sarjerao Aba Gaikwad

Head, Department of Geography

Smt. K.R.P. Kanya Mahavidyalaya Islampur.

Corresponding Author – Dr. Sarjerao Aba Gaikwad

DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.15063465

Abstract:

Textile Industry in India is the second largest employment generator after agriculture. The Textile industry plays important role in the Indian economy and contributes substantially to its export earnings. Textile exports share nearly 30 percent of the country's total exports. It is 20 percent of the National production. It provides direct employment to cover 15 million persons in the mill such as Power Loom and Handloom Sectors. India is the world's second largest production of textiles after china. It is the world's third largest production of cotton. The textile industry in India is one of the oldest manufacturing sectors in the country and currently, its largest in Maharashtra Sangli District plays very important role in textile industry.

The co-operative spinning mill in India is relatively started recently. The co-operative textile sector has played a commendable role in the upliftment of workers in the Krishna Verla Magasvargiya Sahakari soot Girni Ltd Palus here about 10 percent workers are selected as a sample for study This soot Girni is selected in the semi urban area or rural area of Walwa Tehsil the workers are coming from surrounding village of this mill. Therefore, all the study is about a significant socio-economic transformation in the area by this mill. This transformation took the shape of better civic information and a noticeable improvement in the quality-of-life Krishna Verla Magasvargiya Sahakari soot Girni Ltd Palus provided jobs for 490 people. The people are settled nearby the soot Girni around 02 km to 15 km. According to field survey this soot Girni is very useful for change in Socio-Economic conditions of workers. This soot Girni is providing various facilities to workers.

Keywords: Co-Operative Textile Sector, Socio- Economic condition of workers, Manufacturing

Introduction:

The word "Textile" is derived from the Latin word "Texere" meaning to weave and "Textiles" means woven. The word 'Textile' was originally used to define a woven fabric and the process involved in wearing cloth from the ancient time textile industry was working it produced a various type of cloth. Now a days this industry is well established in all over the world.

First Indian textile industry was established in 1822 on the bank of river Hugliin West Bengal. Jute industry made a beginning in 1855 with the establishment of

a jute mill in the Hooghly Valley near Kolkata with foreign capital and entrepreneurship. Thereafter in 1854, the Indian industrialist Mr. Kawasaki Dadabhai Devar had taken initiative and established first modern cotton textile mill at Mumbai (Maharashtra) and after that in 1861, the third textile mill started at Ahmadabad (Gujarat). In the year 1907, the use of electricity has been started in the textile industry and the remarkable development of textile industry has been taking place. At present in India more than 1824 textile mills. Out of these 192 mills are run by the public

sector, 153 are run by the co-operative sector and remaining 1479 textile mills are under the command of private sector.

Maharashtra is an important and leading textile cloth manufacturer state in India because it is not only in number of textile mills but also cloth production and its allied activities. There are 210 cotton textile industries in which 36 per cent looms and 25 per cent spindles out of the total country in Maharashtra. The textile industrial sector of Maharashtra has provided nearly three lakhs employments which contributes different levels of jobs. Mumbai is supposed as the biggest and significant Textile Hub in Maharashtra as well in India. Due to this, Mumbai is known as 'Manchester of India'. Followed the Mumbai, the cotton textile industries are concentrated at Ichalkaranji (Kolhapur district) due to favorable locational factors and it is commonly called as 'Manchester of Maharashtra'. Beside these some other textile centers in Maharashtra which are Sangli, Sholapur, Pune, Jalgaon and Nagpur etc.

Profile of Krishna Verla Magasvargiyasahkari Soot Girni:

This is co-operative spinning mill named as Krishna Verla Sahakari Soot Girni Ltd Palus, is registered on 18 th December 1990 under co-operative Societies Act 1960 of Government of Maharashtra for setting up of a spinning mill. The foundation stone was laid in the year 2004 and actual production was started on 21 st oct 2004. The Society has been organized and promoted by Hon. Dr. Patangrao Kadam who is the distinguished personality and founder of Bharati Vidyapeeth, and Chancellor of Bharathi Vidyapeeth Deemed University which is well known reputed educational organizational at National and State level with its branches in abroad. This mill is successfully running under chairmanship of Prof Babasaheb Gotpagar. This is a state of the art 25056 spindles project, The mill has

complete indigenous machinery of advance technology machines of Kirloskar Toyota, Zincer Textile and the mill has Tromac machine for its Blow Room. In winding the mill had imported latest Germany Schlafthorst 338 Autoconer machines to compute and stand in international market for yarn quality. Also the mill has Imported Laboratory Equipment's of User Technology India Pvt Lets., Switzerland. The set-up of machinery and modern testing equipment results in high production levels and superior quality of yarn. The yarn produced by the mill is accepted by the export markets on all counts of quality standards.

Objective:

1. To Study the facilities provided workers by Soot Girni
2. To Study the socio-economic condition of workers

Methodology and Database:

The primary data has been collected from schedule which has been prepared for workers about 500 workers are working in the Krishna Verla Magasvargiya Sahakari Soot Girni Form these workers about 10 percent workers are selected as sample for this analysis. Here stratified random sample techniques have been used for study. Further the researcher has recorded his observations during the data collection. Also, he had conducted the group discussions to understand the opinion and attitude of the respondents in general. Secondary data has been collected through technical performance report from Maharashtra state co-operative Textile federation Limited Mumbai.

Status of Workers in the Krishna Verla Magasvargiya Sahkari Soot Girni:

Here schedule has been prepared for the analysis of status of workers in the soot Girni. This schedule includes questions regarding their General Information,

Infrastructure and Facilities, Educational status, Family status, Economical status provided by soot Girni. About 49 Schedules

have been filled up from the workers. The workers from different villages, different economical background has been selected.

Table No- -1. Residential Address of the Workers

Sr. No	Local Workers	Out of State Workers	Total Workers
1	44	06	50

Above table shows that majority of the workers are coming from the nearest place of spinning mill. They are travelling 2 km to 18 km distance regularly to work in the spinning mill. Some workers are come here from out of state. (Goa and Karnataka state). Those are stayed in the Kadegaon city. They are invited because they are experienced and skilled workers.

Above table shows that family size between 2 to 4 are in majority worker's house. The second largest group is 4 to 6 because all the workers are forming nearby rural area, which is living in mostly joint family or with their old parents and therefore other peoples of family members are helping them in the agricultural practices.

Table No-2. Education of Workers

Sr. No	Education	Number of Worker
1	S.S.C	22
2	H.S.C	13
3	Graduate	10
4	Post Graduate	05
	Total	50

Above table shows that 44 percent workers are studied up to SSC and 26 percent HSC. This soot Girni is situated in the rural area therefore various workers are coming from rural background. Remaining workers are highly educated those are supervisors and technical workers.

Table No.-4. Work Experience

Sr. No	Work Experience	Number of workers
1	1 Year	27
2	2 Year	05
3	3 Year	09
4	4Year	04
5	More than 5	05
6	Total	50

Majority of the workers are from nearby areas from the shareholders therefore they are not taken for experience. Therefore, here skilled workers are very less. Soot Girni is giving training of machine work after joining. Only few workers are experienced they are mostly from other state of from city specially invited because of their experience.

Table No -3. Family Sizes of Workers

Sr. No	Persons in the family	Number of workers
1	Below-2	08
2	2 to 4	19
3	4 to 6	13
4	6 to 8	06
5	8 to 10	02
	Total	50

Table No.-5. Change in Social Status

Sr. No	Number of workers	Change in social status
1	26	Yes
2	24	No
Total	50	

About 52 percent workers are agreed that their social status has been changed because of this job. They are living in nearby villages they are doing agricultural

practices with this job therefore they can invest better in agriculture than other people. Therefore, they get respect in the village more than only farmers therefore they feel that their social status has been improved.

Conclusion:

This soot Girni is providing job to the people living in the nearby village. Therefore this soot Girni is responsible to improve standard of living of the people lives in nearby village. But majority workers are not experienced. They are doing job because soot Girni is very near to their village and getting additional income. Therefore, they are not serious about job. Workers are having agricultural land and they are doing agricultural practices with this job. Therefore, not focusing on the skill and technology. Therefore for skill and technology soot Girni has appointed persons from out of state. Therefore, here are few suggestions for improving the quality of workers for better development.

- 1) The nature of work in textile units is temporary
- 2) They should provide more health facilities to reduce health problem
- 3) Compulsory training programs

References:

1. Government of Maharashtra (2011). Socio economic Review, Sangli district. Accessed on 05/01/2025. https://mahades.maharashtra.gov.in/files/publication/esm_2011-12_eng.pdf
2. Maharashtra state co-operative Textile federation Limited Mumbai. <https://texcofed.com/>
3. Jagtap, K.N. (2011). Socio economic conditions of displaced power loom workers- A case study
4. Textile commissioner government of India (2012-13) Accessed on 10/01/2025. https://texmin.nic.in/sites/default/files/ar_12_13_english.pdf